

EuroMarine Network Europe's Largest Marine Research Network

From Genes to Ecosystems in
Changing Oceans

Book of Abstracts

EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026

Cádiz, Spain | 10-11 march

Message by the Co-Chairs

The 2026 Open Science Days and General Assembly in Cádiz have concluded, marking a milestone for the EuroMarine Network. We are deeply grateful to everyone who made this event possible and memorable.

We wish to express our sincere thanks to the University of Cádiz (UCA) and the Instituto de Ciencias Marinas de Andalucía (ICMAN-CSIC) for hosting us so graciously. Their institutional support and logistical expertise were invaluable in creating a welcoming environment for our community.

We gratefully acknowledge the generous support of CEIMAR, the SEA-EU Alliance, and the Junta de Andalucía. Their commitment to advancing marine science in the region reflects a shared vision for ocean research excellence.

This book of abstracts celebrates the diverse and outstanding research presented by our keynote speakers, workshop organisers, oral presenters, and poster authors. Your contributions—spanning from fundamental biology to applied conservation, from deep-sea ecosystems to coastal solutions—showcase the breadth and depth of Europe's marine science community.

Finally, we extend heartfelt thanks to the local organising committee members and all participants who travelled to Cádiz to engage with one another, to share ideas, and to forge new collaborations. These conversations will shape the network's priorities and future direction.

We look forward to continuing EuroMarine's mission of bringing together Europe's marine researchers to tackle the pressing challenges facing our oceans.

Simonetta Frascetti
UNINA
Co-Chair, EuroMarine Network

Mark John Costello
NORD
Co-Chair, EuroMarine Network

Acknowledgements

The EuroMarine Network warmly thanks the University of Cádiz (UCA) and the Instituto de Ciencias Marinas de Andalucía (ICMAN-CSIC) for hosting the 2026 Open Science Days and General Assembly. We are grateful to CEIMAR, SEA-EU Alliance, and the Junta de Andalucía for their generous support. Special thanks to all the local organising committee members who made this event possible.

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Agenda

10 March 2026 — Open Science Day

- 12:30 – 13:00 *Arrivals and registration of participants (Edificio Constitución 1812)*
- 13:00 – 13:10 **Welcome by University of Cádiz & CSIC (Salón de Actos, Facultad de Filosofía y Letras)**
María Jesús Ortega, Vice-Rector for Research, UCA & Antonio Tovar, Director ICMAN-CSIC
- 13:10 – 13:20 **CEIMAR & SEA-EU Welcome (Salón de Actos, Facultad de Filosofía y Letras)**
Carmen Garrido (CEI-MAR Scientific Coordinator, UCA) & Marcela Iglesias (General Coordinator of SEA-EU Alliance, UCA)
- 13:20 – 13:30 **Welcome and Introduction by EuroMarine Scientific Coordinators (Salón de Actos, Facultad de Filosofía y Letras)**
Mark John Costello (EuroMarine Co-Chair, NORD) & Simonetta Frascchetti (EuroMarine Co-Chair, UNINA)
- 13:30 – 14:15 Keynote — Seagrasses: From Ecophysiology to Blue Carbon and Restoration**
Juanjo Vergara, Full Professor UCA
- 14:20 – 14:30 **RugOBSS: Satellite Monitoring Platform of the *Rugulopteryx okamurae* invasion**
Mar Roca Mora, CSIC
- 14:30 – 14:40 **Beach metabolic activity associated with massive wrack accumulations of *Rugulopteryx okamurae***
Iván Franco Rodil, UCA
- 14:40 – 14:50 **Intracellular nitrogen storage in Antarctic phytoplankton across two contrasting environments**
Juan Rodríguez-Márquez, UCA
- 14:50 – 15:20 *Coffee Break (Edificio Constitución 1812)*
- 15:20 – 16:10 Keynote — The Strait of Gibraltar: Reading Climate Change at the Ocean's Gateway**
Emma Huertas, CSIC
- 16:10 – 16:20 **Building the foundations of a Digital Twin for a Marine Protected Area through integrated fine-scale observations**
Nikhil Thomas, CMMI
- 16:20 – 16:30 **Rocky refuges matter: microhabitat effects on intertidal sessile invertebrate assemblages**
Bárbara Calvo Ríos, University of Vigo
- 16:30 – 16:40 **Trans-disciplinary and trans-boundary research to assess non-native species in aquaculture**
Barbara Mikac, UNIBO
- 16:40 – 17:00 *Coffee Break (Edificio Constitución 1812)*
- 17:00 – 18:15 Workshop 1: Linking with Social Sciences**

Emma McKinley, Cardiff University

18:15 – 19:30 **Science & Cocktails — Poster Session**

Agenda (continued)

11 March 2026 — Open Science Day

- 8:30 – 9:00 *Registration of participants (Edificio Constitución 1812)*
- 9:00 – 9:45 **Keynote — Life and Element Cycling in the Deepest Oceanic Realm**
Ronnie Glud, SDU
- 9:50 – 10:00 **Microbial Respiration in Expanding Pacific and Indian Oxygen Minimum Zones**
Emilio Garcia-Robledo, UCA
- 10:00 – 10:10 **Governing the Deep Sea: Legal, Ethical, and Environmental Challenges in the Emerging Exploitation of Polymetallic Nodules**
Raquel-Esther Rey Charlo, UCA
- 10:10 – 10:20 **Thriving in the dark: Balearic submarine cave biodiversity**
Daniel Martin, CSIC
- 10:30 – 10:50 *Coffee Break (Edificio Constitución 1812)*
- 10:50 – 11:00 **From Heatwave to Outbreak: A Fish-Viral Outbreak in the Azores**
Ines Gomes, OKEANOS
- 11:00 – 11:10 **Biodiversity and ecosystem services in natural versus restored Adriatic saltmarshes**
Alberto Barausse, University of Padova
- 11:10 – 11:20 **Harnessing Microbiome Insights for Enhanced Seaweed Cultivation**
Myrsini Maria Lymperaki, CCMAR/CIMAR
- 11:30 – 11:40 **Forty years of coastal policy by the Andalusian Government (1982–2022)**
Ángel Arenas, UCA
- 11:40 – 11:50 **An integrated observation and monitoring strategy at regional level, Galicia, Spain**
Fran Saborido-Rey, IIM-CSIC
- 11:50 – 12:00 **Beach user preferences ('Big Five'): An integrated Management Tool**
Rosa Molina Gil, UCA
- 12:10 – 13:30 *Lunch Break (Edificio Constitución 1812)*
- 13:30 – 13:40 **Occurrence, removal and photodegradation of persistent, mobile and toxic compounds (PMTs) in aquatic systems**
Maria Sole Pierandrei, Politecnico di Milano
- 13:40 – 13:50 **Broodstock exposure to the toxic dinoflagellate *Alexandrium minutum* affects gamete proteome in the Pacific oyster *Magallana gigas***
Adeline Marzari, UMR 6539 LEMAR Ifremer

- 13:50 – 14:00 **Occurrence distribution and impact of antibiotics in Contrasting Aquaculture Systems and their surroundings**
Sara Rodriguez-Mozaz, ICRA-CERCA
- 14:10 – 14:20 **The "MOST!" workshop: Application of omics in marine ecotoxicology**
Patricia Pinto, CCMAR/CIMAR
- 14:20 – 14:30 **Genomics-informed modelling: advancing our understanding of non-indigenous species' colonisation and spread**
Marc Rius, CSIC
- 14:30 – 14:40 **The Tropical Atlantic invasion into the Mediterranean – a call for action**
Paolo G. Albano, SZN & University of Vienna
- 14:40 – 14:45 **PulseOcean Summer School**
Nuria Teixido, SZN
- 14:50 – 15:00 **The World Association of Marine Stations (WAMS): A global network for ocean science collaboration**
Axel Miller, SAMS
- 15:00 – 15:10 **LifeWatch ERIC as a Hub for Integrated Marine Biodiversity Research in Europe**
Christos Arvanitidis, Lifewatch ERIC
- 15:10 – 15:30 **JPI Oceans strategy: Advancing knowledge, informing policy, and driving innovation**
Thorsten Kiefer, JPIO
- 15:30 – 15:45 **Round table open discussion**
- 15:45 – 16:00 *Coffee break (Edificio Constitución 1812)*
- 16:00 – 17:30 **Workshop 2: Understanding the Policy Landscape (Online)****
Dennis Naughten, Innosphere

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KEYNOTE LECTURES

K1. Seagrasses: From Ecophysiology to Blue Carbon and Restoration

Juanjo Vergara

Universidad de Cádiz (UCA)

Seagrass meadows are foundational coastal ecosystems that link organism-level processes to ecosystem services such as biodiversity support, coastal protection and long-term carbon sequestration. This session presents a synthesis of more than three decades of research on seagrass ecophysiology and ecosystem functioning, using Cádiz Bay as a natural laboratory to explore how environmental drivers shape seagrass performance, resilience and contribution to blue carbon. Starting at the organismal scale, the session examines how light availability, temperature and nutrient form, particularly the contrasting roles of ammonium and nitrate, regulate seagrass metabolism, carbon allocation and survival. Experimental and field evidence shows how light limitation and eutrophication interact to constrain photosynthesis, reduce carbohydrate reserves and trigger toxicity thresholds, with consequences that scale up from individual plants to meadow stability. At the population and community levels, the presentation explores how seagrass structure influences biodiversity, species interactions and herbivory, highlighting the role of seagrass meadows as ecosystem engineers. Long-term observations reveal the capacity of some Atlantic and Mediterranean seagrass species (as it was the case of *Cymodocea Nodosa*) to acclimate to gradual sea-level rise through depth-related adjustments, while also exposing the limits of this resilience under increasing environmental pressure. The session then broadens to the ecosystem and socio-ecosystem scales, focusing on blue carbon dynamics in seagrasses and adjacent saltmarshes. Drawing on decadal analyses, sediment studies and microbial assessments, it illustrates how vegetated coastal habitats store, transform and stabilize organic carbon over long timescales. Finally, the talk addresses how this scientific knowledge underpins emerging blue carbon standards, restoration strategies and nature-based climate solutions, emphasizing the need for robust methodologies, long-term monitoring and ecosystem-level thinking. Overall, the session highlights how integrating ecophysiology, long-term observation and applied research is essential for effective conservation, restoration and climate-relevant management of seagrass ecosystems.

About the speaker: *Juanjo Vergara is Full Professor at the University of Cádiz, specialising in seagrass ecophysiology, coastal ecosystem functioning and blue carbon, with long-standing experience linking fundamental research, long-term observations and restoration practice.*

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K2. The Strait of Gibraltar: A Natural Laboratory for Climate-Driven Biogeochemical Change

I.Emma Huertas

Instituto de Ciencias Marinas de Andalucía (ICMAN-CSIC)

The Strait of Gibraltar constitutes a key oceanographic gateway for investigating climate-driven changes in marine biogeochemical cycles. As the sole open-ocean connection between the Atlantic Ocean and the Mediterranean Sea, it sustains a persistent two-layer exchange that regulates basin-scale budgets of carbon, nutrients and heat. This unique configuration enables the detection and quantification of climate signals emerging from the interaction between physical circulation and biogeochemical processes. Here, results from nearly two decades of sustained observations at the Gibraltar Fixed Time Series (GIFT) are synthesised. Observational evidence demonstrates a substantial net export of inorganic carbon from the Mediterranean to the Atlantic, coupled with a continuous input of anthropogenic carbon into the Mediterranean basin. Additionally, dissolved organic carbon of Atlantic origin supports a significant fraction of net heterotrophy in the Mediterranean, revealing a tight coupling between lateral transport and ecosystem metabolism. These findings, along with the observed nutrient fluxes, challenge simplified representations of Mediterranean oligotrophy and highlight the role of inter-basin exchange in structuring productivity gradients. High-frequency measurements through moored instruments further document ongoing ocean acidification and warming in both water flows, with decadal trends indicating that a large fraction of the

observed pH decline is driven by natural variability. Projections under high-emission scenarios suggest that critical conditions for biogenic calcification to proceed in the exchanged water masses will be reached before the end of the century. Concurrent warming of Mediterranean Outflow Water reinforces the role of the Strait as a conduit of climate signals across basins. The Strait also facilitates the transport of non-CO₂ greenhouse gases, particularly nitrous oxide, with lateral fluxes between basins largely exceeding local air–sea exchanges. Overall, these results highlight the Strait of Gibraltar as a natural laboratory for resolving coupled physical-biogeochemical processes and underscore the importance of sustained observations to constrain regional and global biogeochemical budgets.

About the speaker: *Emma Huertas is a Research Scientist and Deputy Director at the Instituto de Ciencias Marinas de Andalucía (CSIC), specialising in marine biogeochemistry, air–sea greenhouse gas exchange and ocean–climate interactions.*

Cite this abstract: *Huertas, IE. (2026). The Strait of Gibraltar: A Natural Laboratory for Climate-Driven Biogeochemical Change. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. K2.*

K3. Life and Element Cycling in the Deepest Oceanic Realm

Ronnie N. Glud

University of Southern Denmark (SDU); Tokyo University of Marine Science & Technology; Danish Institute of Advanced Science; Director, Danish Center for HADAL Research

The hadal zone represents the deepest and most scantily explored marine habitats on Earth. The hadal ocean covers more than 2 million km² and includes 27 long, narrow trench systems that stretch along tectonic subduction zones. Hadal exploration is challenging, but recent technical advances have provided new possibilities to explore the deep and have drastically enhanced our knowledge on life and biogeochemistry in the deepest oceanic realm. It has now been documented that trenches act as depocenters for organic material, and they appear to represent globally important sites of carbon sequestration, but at the same time they act as biological hot spots for deep-sea life flourishing at extreme hydrostatic pressure. Microbial mineralisation rates along trench axes are highly intensified as compared to adjacent abyssal plains, and in the most active trench systems early diagenesis includes the complete redox sequence of anaerobic mineralisation known from coastal sediments. The intensified mineralisation is mediated at extreme hydrostatic pressure by largely unexplored communities, and preliminary investigations suggest that hadal biomes are distinct but surprisingly diverse. Recent findings also document that trenches act as depositories for anthropogenic pollutants and can hold surprisingly high inventories of persistent organic pollutants. Hadal trenches are unique but highly dynamic deep-sea environments, and their function or importance cannot be understood by extrapolating insights from the ambient ocean. The presentation will provide an overview of the status of hadal biogeochemical research and discuss the many unresolved questions and paradigms that will spark hadal research in the coming years.

About the speaker: *Ronnie N. Glud is a marine biogeochemist with particular focus on microbial-driven carbon and nitrogen cycling in coastal, deep-sea and hadal settings. His research has been enabled through the development of sophisticated sensor systems and autonomous instrumentation for direct in situ investigations.*

Cite this abstract: *Glud, R.N. (2026). Life and Element Cycling in the Deepest Oceanic Realm. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. K3.*

INTERACTIVE WORKSHOPS

W1. Workshop 1: Linking Marine Sciences with Social Sciences

Emma McKinley

Cardiff University

This interactive workshop explored the vital and evolving connections between marine science and the social sciences. As the challenges facing our ocean become increasingly complex, purely technical or ecological approaches are no longer sufficient; understanding human dimensions is essential. Participants engaged with concepts related to ocean literacy, marine citizenship, and public perceptions of marine and coastal systems. The session aimed to foster interdisciplinary dialogue between marine researchers and social science perspectives, examining how community engagement, governance processes, and societal values shape conservation outcomes. Through a series of interactive activities, attendees shared what inspired them to get involved in ocean research, emphasising the importance and diversity of human-ocean connections for inspiring an interest in ocean careers. Responses included references to family connections, inspiration from ocean champions including Jacques Cousteau, interest in a wide range of species and broader ocean biodiversity, and a 'Love for the ocean and a desire to do something about it'. The next activity explored practical pathways for integrating social science methodologies into marine research programmes and into EuroMarine's strategic activities. First, attendees were asked to highlight examples of projects and initiatives that already exist that could support EuroMarine in engaging more with marine social science research and practice - responses included the OYSTER initiative and other trans-European collaborations. Finally, in groups, attendees identified a broad range of challenges and solutions linked to the integration of marine social science, highlighting issues such as lack of understanding of social science methodologies, a need for improved funding opportunities, calls for improved coordination across the ocean science and research and community and more. The outcomes of this session provide valuable insights that the EuroMarine Network can draw on in their future initiatives.

Cite this abstract: McKinley, E. (2026). *Workshop 1: Linking Marine Sciences with Social Sciences*. In: *EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026*. EuroMarine Network. W1.

W2. Workshop 2: Understanding the Policy Landscape — Translating Science into Action

Dennis Naughten

Innosphere (Online)

This strategic workshop addresses one of the most persistent challenges in marine science: converting complex research findings into clear, actionable policy messages. Participants will explore the architecture of EU and international marine policy frameworks, identifying key decision-making windows and the stakeholders who shape them. The session covers practical communication strategies for reaching non-specialist audiences from policymakers and regulators to industry and civil society, and examines how framing, timing, and trusted intermediaries influence whether scientific evidence is taken up. Drawing on real-world examples from ocean governance, climate adaptation, and marine spatial planning, attendees will leave with a strengthened ability to position their research within the policy landscape and contribute effectively to EuroMarine's science-to-policy mission. Interactive discussions highlighted a diverse range of experiences within the EuroMarine community regarding engagement with policymakers. While around two thirds of participants reported little or no prior experience, others described involvement spanning from occasional interactions at conferences to sustained engagement at regional, national, and international levels. Across this spectrum, participants expressed a shared interest in strengthening science-policy links, with key motivations including co-designing solutions to societal challenges, increasing the impact and visibility of research, and supporting evidence-based decision-making. The exchanges also underscored important considerations such as the need to understand policymakers' priorities, ensure equitable access to engagement opportunities, and maintain the independence of scientific research.

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ORAL PRESENTATIONS

O1. RugOBSS: Satellite monitoring platform of the *Rugulopteryx okamurae* invasion

Mar Roca Mora¹, Maria João Borlido Oliveira Lima², Bede Ffinian Rowe Davies³

¹ Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)

² Center of Marine and Environmental Research (CIMA) - Universidade do Algarve

³ French Institute for Ocean Science (IFREMER)

Rugulopteryx okamurae is an Invasive Alien Species first detected in 2015 in the Strait of Gibraltar, posing severe ecological and socio-economic impacts across Mediterranean and Atlantic coasts. Its rapid expansion and massive beachcast events require large-scale monitoring tools. RugOBSS is an Early-Career Researcher Cooperation Project funded by OYSTER EuroMarine involving Spain, France, and Portugal, aiming to (1) create the first regional database of *R. okamurae* beachcasts in Algarve and Andalusia, (2) analyse spatio-temporal trends of biomass arrivals since 2015, and (3) provide a platform for historical and near-real-time monitoring to support macroalgae biomass management. The *Rugulopteryx okamurae* Observing Beachcast System from Space is an open-source cloud platform using Sentinel-2 imagery (at 10-meter resolution) to quantify beached biomass, cover, and impacted area. Validated with field data, RugOBSS supports objective impact assessment, early detection for operational management, and informed decision-making for invasive species economic compensations and potential valorisation.

Keywords: *invasive species, remote sensing, biomass removal, OYSTER, Sentinel-2*

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O2. Beach metabolic activity associated with massive wrack accumulations of *Rugulopteryx okamurae*

Iván Franco Rodil¹, Valle Pérez-Rodríguez¹, Alejandro Bernal-Ibáñez², Mauro Pardiello³, Federica Soccio³, Ignacio Gestoso¹, Raúl Ochoa-Hueso⁴

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⁴ Vitivinicultural and Agri-Food Research Institute (IVAGRO), University of Cádiz

Macroalgal wrack accumulations are crucial for recycling nutrients and regulating trophic connectivity in sandy beaches. In addition, beach wrack can be considered metabolic hotspots with high activity and rates of CO₂ flux. However, the sudden beaching of huge seaweed masses smothers the coastline, forming rotting piles on the shore. The decomposition of sudden pulses of wrack can modify dramatically the biogeochemistry of beach sands, and the presence of invasive macroalgae may involve deleterious effects on the wrack metabolic activity. We quantified the biomass of *Rugulopteryx okamurae*, a very aggressive invasive species, on five sandy beaches from the Atlantic coast of the Strait of Gibraltar (Spain), and we tested the effects on respiratory CO₂ fluxes using an infrared gas analyser (IRGA). All the beaches showed large accumulations of *Rugulopteryx* wrack deposits, mainly in the intertidal area, ranging from 23.4 ± 5.2 to 96.0 ± 3.2 % (mean ± SE) cover of the sampled area. The biomass changed significantly between beaches, ranging from 968.3 ± 287.7 kg m⁻¹ to 9210 ± 1279.4 kg m⁻¹ (mean ± SE). The wrack patches supported high metabolic activity, with CO₂ fluxes averaging (±SE) 19.15 ± 5.5 μmol C m⁻² s⁻¹, > 5 times as high as that of tropical rain forests. Wrack metabolic rates (mean ± SE) ranged 60-fold across beaches, from a

minimum of 2.04 ± 0.06 to a maximum of $123.1 \pm 59.87 \mu\text{mol C m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. There was considerable within-beach variability in the metabolic rates related to the distance of the wrack from the shoreline, as the average respiration rates tended to increase significantly from the swash to the drift line. Moreover, thicker wrack patches combined with a more degraded algal stage showed significantly higher CO_2 fluxes. Massive amounts of beach wrack accumulations release huge amounts of CO_2 and we suggest they can become a significant source of greenhouse gas emissions. With climate change and increasing anthropogenic waste expected to accelerate the rate of wrack accumulation on beaches, this study provides timely information for developing nearshore carbon budgets.

Keywords: *CO₂, greenhouse gas, Beach management, Metabolic hotspots*

Cite this abstract: Rodil, I.F., Pérez-Rodríguez, V., Bernal-Ibáñez, A., Pardiello, M., Soccio, F., Gestoso, I., Ochoa-Hueso, R. (2026). Beach metabolic activity associated with massive wrack accumulations of *Rugulopteryx okamurae*. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. O2.

O3. Intracellular nitrogen storage in Antarctic phytoplankton across two contrasting environments

Juan Rodríguez-Márquez^{1,2}, Emilio G. García-Robledo^{1,2}, Eugenio Fraile-Nuez³, Gabriel Navarro⁴, Antonio Tovar-Sánchez⁴, I. Emma Huertas⁴, Ana Bartual^{1,2}

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Phytoplankton represent an often-overlooked nitrogen reservoir, being able to remove and accumulate nitrate intracellularly, thus changing the dynamics of the marine nitrogen cycle. To evaluate the relevance of this pool in a particularly productive area of the Southern Ocean, phytoplankton samples were collected inside the Bay of Deception Island (Antarctica) and in water masses surrounding it (Strait of Bransfield) during the 2025 austral summer. Despite non-limiting macronutrient conditions occurred, significant spatial variations in intracellular nitrogen storage were observed. While external oceanic offshore waters showed lower storage, the inshore community exhibited a 3 to 4-fold higher intracellular nitrogen accumulation, accounting for approximately 25% of the total dissolved nitrogen pool. Remarkably, this trend coincided with much lower nitrate levels in inshore waters, suggesting that intracellular partitioning represent an important driver of nitrogen dynamics in this productive Antarctic ecosystem.

Keywords: *Diatoms, nitrate, nitrite, phytoplankton*

Cite this abstract: Rodríguez-Márquez, J., García-Robledo, E.G., Fraile-Nuez, E., Navarro, G., Tovar-Sánchez, A., Huertas, I.E., Bartual, A. (2026). Intracellular nitrogen storage in Antarctic phytoplankton across two contrasting environments. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. O3.

O4. Building the foundations of a Digital Twin for a Marine Protected Area through integrated fine-scale observations

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High-resolution, fine-scale ocean observations remain scarce across the eastern Mediterranean, particularly in coastal and nearshore ecosystems of Cyprus. To address this gap, we aim to establish the architectural foundation for a Digital Twin of a Marine Protected Area (MPA) by coordinating multimodal, fine-scale observations within a common spatial context. The work is being conducted at the Thalassines Spilies MPA and is supported by the PUREEF-Y and eDNA-LEV projects, which enable multidisciplinary monitoring and data generation. The ongoing dataset includes seasonal physicochemical measurements, pollutant and nutrient analyses, intertidal and subtidal ecological surveys, photogrammetry, DNA metabarcoding, incubation experiments, and paleo-environmental reconstructions. While these datasets are currently analysed independently, their coordinated

acquisition establishes a site-specific baseline capturing physical, biogeochemical, and ecological variability at fine scales. This framework represents a critical preparatory step toward future data integration, assimilation, and modelling, offering a transferable pathway for strengthening coastal observing systems and effective management in data-limited MPAs.

Keywords: *Digital Twin, MPA, Shallow water reefs, Cyprus, Levantine Sea*

Cite this abstract: Thomas, N., Cai, L., Christoforou, E., Geldenhuys, G., Gkoulia, A., Hadjiannou, L. (2026). Building the foundations of a Digital Twin for a Marine Protected Area through integrated fine-scale observations. In: *EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. O4.*

O5. Rocky refuges matter: microhabitat effects on intertidal sessile invertebrate assemblages

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University of Vigo

Rocky intertidal shores are structurally complex environments where fine-scale topographic heterogeneity, crevices, overhangs, flat surfaces, and steep faces, creates a mosaic of microclimatic conditions varying substantially in exposure, moisture retention, and thermal stress. Yet the extent to which this microhabitat diversity structures sessile invertebrate assemblages and modulates the physiological performance of ecologically and commercially important species remains poorly understood. This study quantitatively analyses the distribution patterns of *Mytilus galloprovincialis* and *Pollicipes pollicipes* across four contrasting microhabitat types at two rocky shore localities on the Galician coast (NW Spain). Combining assemblage-level multivariate analysis with individual-level physiological indicators; condition index (CI) for mussels and quality ratio (QR) for goose barnacles; across recruit, juvenile, and adult size classes, we show that microhabitat type significantly structures both community composition and species performance, with locality-specific interaction effects. Crevices consistently supported higher mussel condition indices, while steep surfaces favoured barnacle quality ratios. These findings demonstrate that even at centimetre scales, topographic heterogeneity plays a key role in determining the distribution and physiological state of intertidal invertebrates, with implications for stock assessment and the management of harvested species.

Keywords: *rocky intertidal, microhabitat, Mytilus galloprovincialis, Pollicipes pollicipes, condition index, Galician coast*

Cite this abstract: Calvo Ríos, B., Román, M., Olabarria, C. (2026). Rocky refuges matter: microhabitat effects on intertidal sessile invertebrate assemblages. In: *EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. O5.*

O6. Trans-disciplinary and trans-boundary research to assess non-native species in aquaculture

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Since 2019, the University of Bologna is leading research to detect non-native species (NNS) in Adriatic mollusc farms, identify farming practices that promote their spread, and assess farmers' awareness of NNS. Extensive sampling of fauna associated with farmed mussels and oysters was carried out along Italian, Croatian and

Slovenian coasts. Farmers' local ecological knowledge was collected through questionnaires. Analyses based on classical taxonomy and molecular methods revealed new invaders posing threats to aquaculture industry and provided an updated list of NNS in the Adriatic farms. Farmers reported numerous exchanges of molluscs between the Adriatic and other Mediterranean and Atlantic regions, which can involuntarily transport associated fauna. Although aware of NNS-related issues, they showed limited ability to recognize them. Overall, the results highlight the need for future coordinated projects among Mediterranean and Atlantic European countries, involving research institutions, aquaculture sector, and governing bodies, to address the spread of NNS through aquaculture.

Keywords: *Mediterranean, mollusc aquaculture, invasive species, stakeholder engagement, integrative methods*

Cite this abstract: Mikac, B., Fossi, E., Colangelo, M.A., Dessì, S., Prioli, G., Pećarević, M., Bonačić, K., Mavrič, B., Pitacco, V., Costantini, F. (2026). *Trans-disciplinary and trans-boundary research to assess non-native species in aquaculture. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. O6.*

07. Microbial respiration in expanding Pacific and Indian oxygen minimum zones

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Global expansion of Oxygen Minimum Zones (OMZs) is a critical consequence of ocean deoxygenation. In the Pacific and Indian Oceans, vast hypoxic and anoxic layers are driven largely by microbial respiration, which must adapt to increasingly limited oxygen. We investigated how microbial communities tune their respiratory processes during research cruises in these regions. Using onboard incubations, we measured oxygen consumption rates across a wide range of oxygen concentrations with high-sensitivity sensors. Our results demonstrate that microbial communities increase their metabolic affinity for oxygen by modulating the expression of different terminal oxidases. This adaptation allows continued oxygen consumption even as levels vanish, maintaining metabolic activity in extreme environments. These results contribute to the understanding of the processes governing the dynamics of the OMZs and the broader impacts of a deoxygenating ocean.

Keywords: *oxygen, microorganisms, deoxygenation, climate change*

Cite this abstract: Garcia-Robledo, E., Ramirez-Hernandez, I., Calderon-Caro, J., Mecca, M., Rodriguez-Marquez, J. (2026). *Microbial respiration in expanding Pacific and Indian oxygen minimum zones. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. O7.*

08. Governing the Deep Sea: Legal, ethical, and environmental challenges in the emerging exploitation of polymetallic nodules

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The prospective commercial exploitation of polymetallic nodules in the International Seabed Area poses complex legal, environmental, and ethical challenges. The UNCLOS governance framework, managed by the ISA, faces pressure, questioning its adequacy to ensure sustainable activities. The research employed a multidisciplinary methodology, integrating legal analysis with a technical review of deep-sea mining technologies, including collector vehicles and sediment systems, and examining Sponsoring State responsibilities. The analysis reveals significant normative gaps, particularly in the definition and enforcement of State responsibility and the ethical oversight of private contractors. Technologically, evidence shows current systems are insufficient to prevent large-scale environmental impacts, specifically the dispersion of sediment plumes. Without adopting robust, binding exploitation regulations and mandating the use of the best available mitigation technologies, the environmental risks and governance uncertainties remain unacceptably high. These deficiencies compromise the ecological integrity of abyssal ecosystems and risk international disputes over State responsibility.

Keywords: *Law of the Sea, Polymetallic Nodules, Technology, governance, collection equipment; transportation equipment;*

Cite this abstract: Rey Charlo, R.-E., Vázquez Mejías, A.-I., Alcaide Jiménez, J.-I. (2026). Governing the Deep Sea: Legal, ethical, and environmental challenges in the emerging exploitation of polymetallic nodules. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. O8.

O9. Thriving in the dark: Balearic submarine cave biodiversity

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This presentation summarizes current knowledge on the biodiversity and ecological characteristics of submarine coastal karstic caves, including marine and anchialine systems, which are among the least known marine habitats. Field surveys conducted in the Balearic Islands with expert speleologists, documented species composition and environmental gradients. Results reveal highly specialized and fragile communities dominated by endemic species, many confined to a single cave and adapted to extreme conditions of darkness, low nutrients, and reduced oxygen. Several species are new to science, such as the polychaetes *Pollentia perezii* and *Polycirrus burballes*. These findings underscore the ecological uniqueness and vulnerability of these ecosystems, which serve as natural laboratories for studying adaptation and speciation. Protecting submarine caves is essential to preserve their irreplaceable biodiversity and evolutionary processes. To raise public awareness on these hidden ecosystems, we have also developed a virtual reality application offering an immersive experience that simulates a cave dive.

Keywords: *Stygobionts, biodiversity, coastal caves, anchialine caves, virtual reality*

Cite this abstract: Martin, D., Capa, M. (2026). Thriving in the dark: Balearic submarine cave biodiversity. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. O9.

O10. From heatwave to outbreak: A fish viral outbreak in the Azores

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This study addresses the causes and implications of a mass mortality event affecting wild groupers in the Azores during the 2024 marine heatwave (MHW). Field sampling, histopathology, molecular diagnostics, and genetic analyses were conducted on affected dusky grouper (*Epinephelus marginatus*) and island grouper (*Mycteroperca fusca*). Results confirmed the first viral nervous necrosis (VNN) outbreak in wild *E. marginatus* in the North Atlantic and the first detection of the virus in *M. fusca*. Infected fish exhibited typical VNN lesions, and viral sequences were highly homogeneous (>99% similarity), indicating a single recent introduction. The outbreak coincided with a strong MHW, with sea surface temperatures above 25 °C, favoring virus replication. The predominance of adult mortalities raises concerns for population sustainability. This event underscores the vulnerability of long-lived, site-attached species to emerging pathogens under warming seas and highlights the need for coordinated monitoring and early warning systems.

Keywords: *Viral Nervous Necrosis, Groupers, Climate Change, Ocean Warming, Epizootic, North Atlantic*

Cite this abstract: Gomes, I., Novoa-Pabón, A., Abbadi, M., Pretto, T., Rosa, J., Silva, L., Paulo, T., Marsella, A., Afonso, P., Toffan, A. (2026). From heatwave to outbreak: A fish viral outbreak in the Azores. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. O10.

O11. Biodiversity and ecosystem services in natural versus restored Adriatic saltmarshes

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Saltmarshes are threatened by human activities and have lost about half of their global surface. Along the north-western Adriatic coast, once-widespread saltmarshes are much reduced due to, e.g., land reclamation, sea level rise, and human-driven erosion. Although large-scale saltmarsh restoration investments were made over the past few decades, mainly through active approaches such as sediment nourishment, few studies have assessed their outcomes, especially on ecologically relevant medium-long timescales. This study synthesizes monitoring carried out over the past few years in the Venice and Caorle lagoons to compare natural and restored salt marshes in terms of biodiversity (e.g. plant community coverage and composition, fish biomass in near-by waters), morphology (elevation) and services (e.g. N and C storage, commercial fish species). Importantly, plant communities and related services typically differ across natural and restored salt marshes. Differences could be ascribed to human-controllable factors (elevation, soil grain sizes), highlighting good practices and mistakes to avoid when restoring these threatened habitats.

Keywords: saltmarshes, restoration, ecosystem services, good practices, halophyte vegetation

Cite this abstract: Barausse, A. (2026). Biodiversity and ecosystem services in natural versus restored Adriatic saltmarshes. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. O11.

O12. Harnessing microbiome insights for enhanced seaweed cultivation

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Seaweed-associated microbial communities are crucial for host functions, including nutrient uptake, morphogenesis, and protection against stressors, with their composition influenced by environmental factors and the host's life cycle. This study aimed to isolate and characterize the culturable bacteriome of the macroalgae *Ulva*, *Codium*, *Gelidium*, and *Laminaria* from natural habitats and Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) systems, while assessing seasonal dynamics and composition of their associated uncultured microbial communities. Culturable strains were isolated using two media and identified via full-length 16S rRNA gene amplicon Sanger sequencing, whereas uncultured microbial communities were analyzed using Illumina MiSeq. Over 700 bacterial isolates were obtained, many of which exhibited beneficial properties. Illumina analysis revealed significant microbial diversity variation across seasons and cultivation conditions. A novel image segmentation-based method, *Ulva* growth rate was compared under different bacterial inoculations. These findings provide insights into microbiome manipulations that interact with macroalgal stress physiology, supporting innovation in the seaweed industry.

Keywords: Seaweed, microbial communities, microbiome manipulations, 16S rRNA, IMTA

Cite this abstract: Lympiraki, M.M., Brazão, J.M., Aires, T., Martins, M., Mendes, M.C., Oliveira, I., Alves-Lima, C., Filipe, J.L., Camacho, R., Engelen, A.H. (2026). Harnessing microbiome insights for enhanced seaweed cultivation. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. O12.

O13. Forty years of coastal policy by the Andalusian Government (1982-2022)

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University of Cadiz

Coastal areas are among the most densely populated and environmentally pressured worldwide, and Andalusia, the largest coastal region of Spain, is no exception. Despite the central role of the Andalusian Governing Council (AGC) in regional governance, its coastal-related political output has not been systematically analysed. This study aims to quantitatively examine the evolution of coastal policy decisions adopted by the AGC between 1982 and 2022. We applied statistical analysis to 965 coastal-related decisions individually identified from a total of 38,326 decisions. Statistical analysis reveal a moderate but significant increase of mixed-type decisions ($\tau=0.57$, $p<.05$), alongside consistent growth in Regional Ministries combining environmental and primary sector responsibilities ($\tau=0.648$, $p<.05$). Actors analysis highlights predominance of public institutions, accounting for over 50% of decisions in all legislatures. The findings reveal the absence of a sustained and specialised coastal policy in Andalusia, characterised by reactive measures and a gradual, non-specialised shift toward integrated approaches.

Keywords: Coastal Management, Coastal Zone, Andalusia, Andalusian Governing Council, Public Policy

Cite this abstract: Arenas, Á., Barragán, J.M. (2026). Forty years of coastal policy by the Andalusian Government (1982-2022). In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. O13.

O14. An integrated observation and monitoring strategy at regional level, Galicia, Spain

Fran Saborido-Rey¹, Garbiñe Ayensa², Eva Balsa¹, Juan Bellas³, Marta Casas¹, Marisa Fernández⁴, Ramón Gesteira⁵, José Molares², Daniel Rey⁵, Belén Rubio⁵, Manuel Ruiz-Villarreal³, Juan Taboada⁶, Silvia Torres⁴

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An EU funded initiative has developed an integrated regional marine observation and monitoring strategy in Galicia, Spain, a region strongly dependent on marine resources and shaped by a complex upwelling ecosystem. More than 200 researchers from 14 Galician institutions have produced: i) the Integrated Strategy that includes a participatory governance of marine monitoring, enhanced coordination, services, and data policies; ii) 35 new and innovative observation technologies, highly automated tools and platforms to enable sustained data collection, particularly for variables lacking commercial solutions; iii) An integrated marine Big Data Platform following FAIR principles, connected to international infrastructures and including a Marine Virtual Laboratory for data visualisation and use; and iv) Multi scale, transdisciplinary marine simulators that integrates data, assess global change impacts and support knowledge-based decision making. The result will lead to better-informed decision-making for the modernization and reinforcement of marine observation and monitoring as a foundation for a robust social, economic and environmental resilience, enabling sustainable use of Galicia's marine ecosystems.

Keywords: Monitoring, Big Data Platform, Observation Technologies, Marine Simulators, Digital Twin

Cite this abstract: Saborido-Rey, F., Ayensa, G., Balsa, E., Bellas, J., Casas, M., Fernández, M., Gesteira, R., Molares, J., Rey, D., Rubio, B., Ruiz-Villarreal, M., Taboada, J., Torres, S. (2026). An integrated observation and monitoring strategy at regional level, Galicia, Spain. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. O14.

O15. Beach user preferences ('Big Five'): An integrated management tool

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The study develops a semiquantitative management tool based on the BARE system to improve the assessment of coastal bathing areas. The methodology is structured into four sequential phases designed to operationalize the “Big Five” criteria—safety, facilities, water quality, absence of solid waste, and scenery—across different beach types. First, detailed information is collected for each parameter and beach category. Second, each Big Five element is evaluated using an A–D scoring scale to standardize qualitative observations. Third, beaches are classified into a 1–5 star rating system derived from the previous assessment. Finally, the results are integrated into a beach management model aimed at supporting decision making. This methodology will be applied to 60 beaches in Cádiz (Spain), generating practical outputs such as a tourist guide. The approach provides local administrations with a structured tool for improving beach quality and helps users select beaches according to their preferences.

Keywords: Coastal assessment; Beach management; BARE system; Beach quality; semiquantitative tool

Cite this abstract: Molina, R., Anfuso, G. (2026). Beach user preferences ('Big Five'): An integrated management Tool. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. O15.

O16. Occurrence, removal and photodegradation of persistent, mobile and toxic compounds (PMTs) in aquatic systems

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Persistent, mobile and toxic (PMT) compounds are emerging contaminants of rising concern because they persist and spread in the environment, threatening ecosystems and human health. This study evaluates the occurrence, removal, and photodegradation of 80 PMTs to determine their fate in an aquatic system of southern Spain under conventional treatment conditions and sunlight. Water samples from the Guadalete River and influent and effluent samples from the Jerez de la Frontera wastewater treatment plant were collected in March 2022. Laboratory photodegradation experiments following OECD guidelines evaluated selected PMTs behaviour under photolytic processes. Some compounds break down rapidly under photolytic conditions, such as 3-((4-methylphenyl)sulfonyl)carbamoyl)amino)phenyl 4-methylbenzenesulfonate (84% in 20 hours). Others degrade more slowly, such as Tris[2-chloro-1-(chloromethyl)ethyl] phosphate (32%), while Tris(2-chloroethyl)phosphate shows little to no degradation. Photodegradation kinetics and half-lives will be determined for degraded compounds. Results highlight the persistence of PMTs in the environment and the role of photodegradation as a compound-dependent attenuation pathway in aquatic systems.

Keywords: Persistent, Mobile, Toxic, Photodegradation, Environment

Cite this abstract: Pierandrei, M.S., Freemantle, L.J.E., Lara Martín, P.A. (2026). Occurrence, removal and photodegradation of persistent, mobile and toxic compounds (PMTs) in aquatic systems. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. O16.

O17. Broodstock exposure to the toxic dinoflagellate *Alexandrium minutum* affects gamete proteome in the Pacific oyster *Magallana gigas*

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The toxic dinoflagellate *Alexandrium minutum* can produce paralytic shellfish toxins, as well as bioactive extracellular compounds, harmful for marine organisms. Studies demonstrated that parental exposure to *Alexandrium* spp. impair reproduction and larval development in bivalves. Nevertheless, the molecular mechanisms underlying these intergenerational effects remain unknown. In this study, we exposed adult oysters to *A. minutum* during gametogenesis: either at the initiation or the mature stage. We analyzed the effects on gametes and offspring and characterized the responses at the molecular level in gametes using a quantitative proteomic approach. While no major effects were observed at the phenotypic level in adults and their offspring, several proteins, particularly in oocytes, displayed modifications in their abundance. Overall, the differentially abundant proteins were involved in various biological activities such as cytoskeleton, lipid metabolism, cell cycle and response to oxidative stress, which could impair gamete fertilization and early embryo-development in the Pacific oyster.

Keywords: Harmful algal blooms, Paralytic shellfish toxins, Bivalves, Gametogenesis, Proteomics

Cite this abstract: Marzari, A., Bernay, B., Artigaud, S., Legoic, N., Leluyer, J., Koechlin, H., Hégaret, H., Rivière, G., Fabioux, C. (2026). Broodstock exposure to the toxic dinoflagellate *Alexandrium minutum* affects gamete proteome in the Pacific oyster *Magallana gigas*. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. O17.

O18. Occurrence distribution and impact of antibiotics in Contrasting Aquaculture Systems and their surroundings

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1. Objectives: This study aimed to assess the occurrence, distribution, and associated environmental and human health risks of antibiotics in contrasting aquaculture systems, including a coastal open-water mariculture facility and a land-based recirculating aquaculture system (RAS). 2. Methodology: Sampling campaigns were conducted at an antibiotic-free mariculture site in Liguria and at a commercial RAS facility in Tuscany, Italy. Selected antibiotics were analyzed in seawater, sediments, farmed fish, and surrounding biota using SPE or QUEChERS extraction followed by UPLC–MS/MS. Potential environmental and human health risks posed by the presence of antibiotics were calculated. 3. Results: Across both systems, sulfonamides, macrolides, quinolones, and nitroimidazoles were frequently detected, with seawater concentrations reaching up to 46 ng/L. Several antibiotics posed moderate to high environmental risks ($RQ > 1$), while antibiotics detected in fish did not indicate any human health risks ($HQ < 0.1$). 4. Conclusion/Implications: Despite differing system designs, both aquaculture settings showed evidence of external antibiotic contamination, highlighting the need for continuous monitoring and mitigation strategies to protect aquatic ecosystems and aquaculture sustainability.

Keywords: Micropollutants; Marine pollution; aquaculture, Environmental risk; Coastal waters

Cite this abstract: Rodríguez-Mozaz, S., Otaiza-González, S., Castaño-Ortiz, J.M., Lozano, I.E., Luna, G.M., Quero, M.G., Massaccesi, N. (2026). Occurrence distribution and impact of antibiotics in Contrasting Aquaculture Systems and their surroundings. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. O18.

O19. The "MOST!" Workshop: Application of Omics in Marine Ecotoxicology

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The "MOST!" workshop addressed the urgent need to modernize environmental and regulatory toxicology in response to the rapidly expanding chemical landscape. Conventional approaches are slow, resource-intensive, and insufficient to assess thousands of data-poor chemicals, particularly for marine and non-model species. Experts highlighted how omics technologies (i.e., transcriptomics, proteomics, lipidomics, epigenetics, metagenomics) provide holistic and mechanistically informative tools to identify modes of action, critical life-stage vulnerabilities, and early molecular perturbations predictive of adverse outcomes. Case studies demonstrated the value of dose-response transcriptomics, toxicogenomic points of departure, evolutionary inference, and multi-omics integration for supporting Weight-of-Evidence and regulatory decision-making. The workshop also emphasized the importance of standardization and FAIR data practices to enable reproducibility and regulatory implementation of toxicogenomic findings. In conclusion, this work is leading the definition of a roadmap that, from multi-omics data to bioinformatics workflows and reporting standards, promises to accelerate the identification of chemical hazards in the marine environment.

Keywords: Toxicogenomics, Multi-omics, Adverse Outcome Pathway, Marine ecotoxicology, Regulatory toxicology

Cite this abstract: Pinto, P., Fernandez-Miguez, M., Katsiadaki, I., Dumollard, R., Miglioli, A. (2026). The "MOST!" Workshop: Application of Omics in Marine Ecotoxicology. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. O19.

O20. Genomics-informed modelling: advancing our understanding of non-indigenous species' colonisation and spread

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Recent research progress in both population genomics and predictive modelling is greatly enhancing the scope and breadth of non-indigenous species (NIS) studies. Population genomics allow detection of both genetic connectivity and signals of adaptation that may aid NIS spread. At the same time, predictive modelling, including approaches such as ecological niche modelling (ENM), are improving our predictions of future NIS distributions. Despite clear complementarity between population genomics and predictive modelling, the combined use of these approaches is not yet commonplace. Here, we show how the combined use of ENM and genomics (e.g. genomics-informed modelling studies) both improve our understanding of NIS' colonisation and establishment and help our predictions of NIS spread and origin. Future research using genomics and ENM in combination is expected to significantly advance our knowledge of the invasion process and help develop more effective NIS management actions

Keywords: invasive species, marine biological invasions, genomics, species distribution modelling

Cite this abstract: Rius, M., Pascual, M. (2026). Genomics-informed modelling: advancing our understanding of non-indigenous species' colonisation and spread. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. O20.

O21. The Tropical Atlantic invasion into the Mediterranean – a call for action

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Even scenarios of moderate global warming may bring the Mediterranean Sea to a state not dissimilar from the Last Interglacial stage (135–116 ka, Upper Pleistocene) when tropical Atlantic species settled in the basin but then regressed into the tropical belt with the following glaciation. The realization of this prediction in a basin already affected by the massive biological invasion via the Suez Canal would lead to its final tropicalization, unprecedented and unrestorable at human time scales. Ecologists, taxonomists, palaeontologists, oceanographers across the entire Mediterranean and the tropical Atlantic Ocean are called to an interdisciplinary collaborative effort to establish a conceptual framework, a monitoring scheme and predictive tools to detect, track and respond to this new wave of tropical invaders.

Keywords: Tropicalization, global warming, range extensions, modelling, adaptation

Cite this abstract: Albano, P.G., Danise, S. (2026). The Tropical Atlantic invasion into the Mediterranean – a call for action. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. O21.

O22. The World Association of Marine Stations (WAMS): A global network for ocean science collaboration

Axel Miller, Matt Frost

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Marine stations have been at the forefront of ocean science for over a century, providing essential infrastructure for research, education, and long-term observation. Despite their global distribution—nearly a thousand coastal laboratories worldwide—their collective potential has remained underutilised. The World Association of Marine Stations (WAMS) was established to address this gap by creating a unified, international framework for collaboration among marine stations and their networks. Formally launched following the First World Congress of Marine Stations in 2021, WAMS brings together leading marine station networks to strengthen partnerships, share resources, and mobilize scientific capacity to meet pressing global challenges. Its mission is to provide a common voice for marine research and policy, foster interdisciplinary science, and support initiatives in education, training, citizen science, and public engagement. WAMS also aims to play a pivotal role in coordinating global monitoring efforts and facilitating capacity building, utilising mechanisms such as the Global Atlas of Marine Stations and international bursary schemes. By connecting marine stations across regions, WAMS contributes to the objectives of the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, enabling integrated responses to climate change, biodiversity loss, and ocean sustainability. This presentation will outline WAMS' vision, governance, and current activities, highlighting opportunities for engagement and collaboration within this growing global network.

Keywords: Marine stations, global collaboration, UN Ocean Decade, capacity building.

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O23. LifeWatch ERIC as a Hub for Integrated Marine Biodiversity Research in Europe

[Christos Arvanitidis](#)¹, [Cristina Huertas](#)², [Joaquin López](#)², [Julio Paneque](#)², [Matthias Obst](#)³, [Carlota Muniz](#)⁴, [Johannes Nowe](#)⁴, [Hanneloor Heynderickx](#)⁴, [Natalya Gallo](#)⁵, [Andrés Peredo Arce](#)⁶, [Artūras Razinkovas-Baziukas](#)⁶

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This contribution examines LifeWatch ERIC's role as a hub for integrating marine biodiversity and ecosystem research capacities across Europe within the EuroMarine community under an open-science framework. We analyse outputs from multiple EU-funded marine projects to show how LifeWatch ERIC enables cross-disciplinary research through federated digital infrastructures, semantically interoperable data workflows, and scalable Virtual Research Environments. By combining ontology-based metadata harmonisation, workflow orchestration, cloud-native computation, machine-actionable DMP and FAIR principles, LifeWatch ERIC supports standardised pipelines for data integration, biodiversity assessment, ecosystem modelling, and automated KPI generation. Case studies from EU projects such as ANERIS, MARBEFES, MARCO-BOLO, and Marine SABRES demonstrate that LifeWatch ERIC may well serve as a central integration layer or hub that improves methodological consistency, reproducibility, and cross-project comparability, while reducing fragmentation across scientific domains. Overall, the findings highlight the strategic value of coordinated research infrastructures in accelerating knowledge production and supporting integrated marine ecosystem monitoring and evidence-based policy processes in Europe.

Keywords: *Marine biodiversity, Ecosystem modelling, Data interoperability, Virtual Research Environments, Open science*

Cite this abstract: Arvanitidis, C., Huertas, C., López, J., Paneque, J., Obst, M., Muniz, C., Nowe, J., Heynderickx, H., Gallo, N., Arce, A.P., Razinkovas-Baziukas, A. (2026). LifeWatch ERIC as a Hub for Integrated Marine Biodiversity Research in Europe. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. O23.

O24. JPI Oceans Strategy: Advancing knowledge, informing policy, and driving innovation

[Thorsten Kiefer](#)

JPI Oceans

This contribution outlines the strategic role of JPI Oceans as a pan-European platform aligning national marine research and innovation efforts to address complex, transboundary ocean challenges. It presents how JPI Oceans advances knowledge production, strengthens science–policy interfaces, and fosters innovation through flexible joint actions, coordinated research programming, and strategic engagement with European and international policy frameworks. By promoting co-designed priorities, variable participation, and cross-sector collaboration, JPI Oceans enhances coherence, reduces fragmentation, and improves the policy relevance and impact of marine and maritime research. Overall, the contribution highlights the value of coordinated transnational research infrastructures in supporting informed decision-making and sustainable ocean governance.

Keywords: *Science-policy interface, transnational research coordination, Ocean governance*

Cite this abstract: Kiefer, T. (2026). JPI Oceans Strategy: Advancing knowledge, informing policy, and driving innovation. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. O24.

POSTER PRESENTATIONS

P1. Catch and Effort Dynamics of Small Pelagic Fisheries in São Tomé and Príncipe: Implications for Sustainable Management

Wilfred Boa Morte Zacarias

Institute of Marine Sciences – OKEANOS, University of the Azores

Small-scale artisanal fishing for small pelagic species in São Tomé and Príncipe is one of the main pillars of food security and income generation in the archipelago. This study aimed to characterize small-scale artisanal fishing (SSAF), focused on the capture of small coastal pelagic species, and to assess the impacts of fishing pressure on stocks. A descriptive-analytical model supported by quantitative and comparative approaches was used, integrating data on species caught, fishing effort, productivity, and socioeconomic conditions of coastal communities. The data analyzed comes from historical landing series (1952–2024) and recent surveys (2021–2024), collected by the Directorate of Fisheries and Aquaculture (DPA), through the Department of Research, Statistics, and Aquaculture (DIEA), under the FISH4ACP program. The information includes records of effort and catch, vessel characteristics, and types of gear used. Eight priority small pelagic stocks were analyzed, represented by species such as *Caranx crysos*, *Euthynnus alletteratus*, *Hemiramphus balao*, *Cheilopogon melanurus*, *Decapterus macarellus*, *Sardinella aurita*, *Seriola rivoliana*, and *Decapterus punctatus*. The results revealed complex dynamics and a strong dependence of coastal communities on pelagic resources. Declining trends were observed in several species and an increase in fishing effort (trips and hours at sea), accompanied by fluctuations in CPUE, indicating a relative reduction in productivity. There was also marked seasonal variation, associated with periods of greater concentration of fish schools. From a socioeconomic perspective, there was high dependence on artisanal fishing, low profitability, and vulnerability to environmental and market changes. It was concluded that there are signs of overfishing and a need for effective public policies aimed at participatory management, continuous monitoring, and the adoption of sustainable practices, ensuring the conservation of stocks and the resilience of fishing communities in São Tomé and Príncipe.

Keywords: *Artisanal fishing, Small Pelagic fish, Fisheries management, São Tomé and Príncipe, fishing effort, sustainability*

Cite this abstract: *Zacarias, W.B.M. (2026). Catch and Effort Dynamics of Small Pelagic Fisheries in São Tomé and Príncipe: Implications for Sustainable Management. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P1.*

P2. Unsupervised learning on the Sentinel-2 series in the Mar Menor.

Paola Barba Ceballos¹, Sergio Heredia¹, Gabriel Navarro¹, Belén Rosado², Mar Roca¹, Isabel Caballero¹

¹ *Paola, Sergio, Gabriel, Mar, Isabel - Institute of Marine Sciences of Andalusia (ICMAN), Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)*

² *Belén - Laboratory of Astronomy, Geodesy and Cartography, Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Sciences, University of Cadiz*

The Mar Menor has undergone significant degradation in its ecosystem over the past decade. This coastal lagoon, considered the most important in Europe, is continuously monitored with the purpose of implementing more effective protection and restoration measures. In this work, Machine Learning techniques and advanced statistical methods are applied to the historical Sentinel-2 series, from July 2015 to June 2024, with the aim of distinguishing areas with similar behavior based on water-quality indices, chlorophyll-a, and turbidity, using a resolution of 10 m. In addition, the temporal evolution of these water-quality indices is analyzed, and the seasonality, long-trend, and irregularities of each area are determined. This spatio-temporal assessment relates extreme events that have occurred in the lagoon to anomalies observed in the data and contributes to a better understanding of the ecological processes affecting the Mar Menor.

Keywords: *k-means; STL decomposition; Copernicus programme; Zoning; Eutrophication.*

Cite this abstract: Barba Ceballos, P., Heredia, S., Navarro, G., Rosado, B., Roca, M., Caballero, I. (2026). Unsupervised learning on the Sentinel-2 series in the Mar Menor. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P2.

P3. Emc2 educational project – safeguarding white crowberry from extirpation in coastal habitats

Alexandra Abreu Lima

MARE - Marine and Environmental Sciences Centre,

ARNET - Aquatic Research Network Associate Laboratory, NOVA School of Science and Technology, NOVA University Lisbon

Coastal habitats with endemic plants – i.e., plants that exist only there and nowhere else in the world – such as the Iberian white crowberry – ‘camarinha’ in Portuguese, ‘camarina’ in Spanish -*Corema album* (L.) D. Don, which is an Iberian endemic, are legacies of unique evolutionary histories but prone to extirpation. Therefore, since 2016, the Emc2 project ‘Exploring white crowberry coastal habitats’ is an educational project aimed to raise awareness and involve young people in conservation actions of declining white crowberry populations. Results obtained from white crowberry propagation and plant reintroduction at wild, in Caminha coastal habitats (North), during 2018 and 2025, were successful and reveal it is possible to avoid this plant extirpation. These results were included in global portal ‘Panorama Solutions’ and can be replicated to other Iberian coastal zones to enrich school curricula and empower young people in coastal ecosystems restoration, during the United Nations Decade on Ecosystem Restoration.

Keywords: *Corema album*, coastal habitat, extirpation, biodiversity, education

Cite this abstract: Lima, A.A. (2026). Emc2 educational project – safeguarding white crowberry from extirpation in coastal habitats. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P3.

P4. Assessing the environmental status of the western Mediterranean Sea

Ben Möller¹, Miquel Ortega¹, Marta Coll¹

¹ CSIC - Instituto de Ciencias del Mar (ICM)

This work investigated the effect of anthropogenic pressures on the environmental status of the western Mediterranean Sea. It presents the regions first integrated assessment of environmental status within the framework of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD). Conducted at the Institut de Ciències del Mar, the study used the Nested Environmental Assessment Tool (NEAT) to combine an extensive amount of modelled and measured data. The results showed that the western Mediterranean does not achieve Good Environmental Status (GES) on a basin-wide scale, with moderate ecological status across all sub-regions. The degraded conditions of several ecosystem components, specifically those associated with seafloor integrity and biodiversity, were the primary drivers of this status, indicating an extensive effect of anthropogenic pressures. Despite restrictions in data availability, this study represents a critical step towards a standardized methodology for evaluating marine environmental status. The incorporation of modelled data substantially enhanced the scope of the assessment.

Keywords: Ecosystem health; NEAT; Good Environmental Status; Marine Strategy Framework Directive; Integrative Status Assessment;

Cite this abstract: Möller, B., Ortega, M., Coll, M. (2026). Assessing the environmental status of the western Mediterranean Sea. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P4.

P5. Use and applications of unmanned aerial vehicles in polar research

Gabriel Navarro, Alejandro Román, Antonio Tovar-Sánchez

Institute of Marine Sciences of Andalusia (ICMAN-CSIC)

This study aims to demonstrate the potential of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) as efficient, accurate, and low-impact tools for environmental research in polar regions. UAV surveys were conducted during several Antarctic campaigns using RGB, multispectral, hyperspectral, thermal, and LiDAR sensors, and processed through Structure-from-Motion photogrammetry and RTK-supported workflows to generate high-resolution geospatial products. The main outcome is the open-access ShetlandsUAVmetry dataset, comprising more than 15,000 high-resolution optical images and derived photogrammetric products from 28 UAV flights, including orthomosaics, digital surface models, point clouds, and 3D meshes with centimetre-scale accuracy. These data enable detailed mapping of coastal habitats, geomorphology, vegetation, and wildlife-related features in remote and logistically challenging environments. The results highlight UAV technology as a transformative approach for Antarctic research, enhancing environmental monitoring capabilities, reducing disturbance to vulnerable ecosystems, and providing valuable datasets to support climate-change studies and long-term.

Keywords: *Antarctica, UAV, penguin colonies, Hyperspectral, multispectral, RGB*

Cite this abstract: Navarro, G., Román, A., Tovar-Sánchez, A. (2026). Use and applications of unmanned aerial vehicles in polar research. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P5.

P6. Applications of unmanned aerial vehicles for coastal marine monitoring

Roc Xanxo-Prilló, Alejandro Román, Antonio Tovar, Gabriel Navarro

Institute of Marine Sciences of Andalusia (ICMAN-CSIC)

This study aims to demonstrate the potential of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) as a high-resolution remote sensing platform for monitoring marine, estuarine, and polar ecosystems. Multispectral and hyperspectral UAV surveys were conducted across a range of coastal, estuarine, and polar environments to assess water quality, map benthic vegetation and aquaculture infrastructures, monitor invasive macroalgae, quantify microphytobenthic biomass, and characterize coastal habitats under extreme conditions. The results show that UAV data enable accurate retrieval of chlorophyll-a in both water and sediments, high-accuracy discrimination of submerged vegetation, precise mapping of aquaculture structures, effective detection of invasive macroalgae, and estimation of microphytobenthic biomass at centimetre-to-millimetre spatial resolution. These findings highlight UAVs as a robust and flexible tool that complements satellite observations, supporting high-resolution ecosystem monitoring, climate-change research, and evidence-based management in dynamic marine, estuarine, and polar environments.

Keywords: *drones, multispectral, machine learning, marine, remote sensing*

Cite this abstract: Xanxo-Prilló, R., Román, A., Tovar, A., Navarro, G. (2026). Applications of unmanned aerial vehicles for coastal marine monitoring. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P6.

P7. Spatiotemporal distribution of *Physalia physalis* strandings along the Spanish coast.

Itziar Álvarez-Trasobares, Laura Prieto

Institute of Marine Sciences of Andalusia (ICMAN-CSIC)

Physalia physalis sightings along the Spanish coastline has aroused growing interest in understanding its distribution and coastal arrival dynamics. This study analyzes records collected by the Andalusian Institute of Marine Sciences (ICMAN-CSIC) between 2005 and 2025 across Spain's main coastal regions to identify recurring patterns, interannual variability, and regional differences. Results show that the Canary Islands maintain a relatively constant annual presence during the first months of the year (January–March), although event intensity fluctuates. In contrast, the Gulf of Cadiz and the Mediterranean shoreline show linked arrival events, with Mediterranean sightings occurring after those in the Gulf of Cadiz. Shared atmospheric and oceanic patterns drive

the episodes, while the specific conditions of the western Mediterranean modulate it. Finally, the Cantabrian coast shows a distinct pattern, with arrivals mainly during the second half of the year (June–December) and near-annual occurrences in the last decade that varies in its intensity. This analysis presents an integrated view of the spatiotemporal distribution of *Physalia physalis* in Spain and establishes a foundation for future research on the oceanographic and meteorological conditions that influence its arrival along the coast.

Keywords: Portuguese Man-O-War, Spanish coast, stranding patterns, coastal ecology.

Cite this abstract: Álvarez-Trasobares, I., Prieto, L. (2026). Spatiotemporal distribution of *Physalia physalis* strandings along the Spanish coast. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P7.

P8. Mapping intertidal microphytobenthos using machine learning on multispectral drone imagery

Daniel Febles, Alejandro Román, Roc Xanxo, Gabriel Navarro, Sara Haro

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Tidal flats are often covered by microphytobenthos (MPB), a photosynthetic microbial community that grows on the sediment surface and provides important ecosystem services, including climate regulation through primary production and carbon sequestration. Therefore, developing methodologies to identify and monitor intertidal areas covered by MPB is crucial for their conservation. In this study, 15 drone-based multispectral flights were conducted during low tide over three days, covering ~ 14 ha of tidal flats in the inner Cadiz Bay (Spain). A comparison between different machine learning algorithms has been carried out to classify pixels representing the presence of MPB. The results demonstrate the potential of coupling high-resolution spectral and spatial imaging provided by drones with emerging machine learning approaches to monitor intertidal systems at fine spatial scales, enabling improved understanding and management of these ecologically important areas.

Keywords: Unmanned Aerial Vehicle; Artificial Intelligence; Supervised learning; multispectral; microphytobenthos

Cite this abstract: Febles, D., Román, A., Xanxo, R., Navarro, G., Haro, S. (2026). Mapping intertidal microphytobenthos using machine learning on multispectral drone imagery. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P8.

P9. Decision-support tool for sustainable tourism planning in at-risk coastal destinations

María Maestro, Juan Adolfo Chica Ruiz, Manuel Arcila Garrido, María de Andrés García, Gema Ramírez Guerrero, Javier García Onetti, Beatriz Gasalla López

University of Cádiz

BLUETOURL is the main outcome of the CosturA project (PCM_00040) and is presented as a methodological tool aimed at assessing the performance and climate risk of coastal tourism destinations. The objective of this project was to develop an operational model capable of integrating, within a single diagnosis, the functional structure of the tourism system, its development potential, its vulnerability to climate change and its resilience capacity, in order to support sustainable tourism planning and strategic decision-making. The methodology is based on a multidimensional approach structured around four indices applied at both resource and destination scales and subsequently digitalised into an automated tool. The model was applied to the case study of La Caleta (Cádiz, Spain). The results identified key resources, functional imbalances and climate-vulnerable elements, generating an integrated diagnosis with a SWOT analysis and strategic action proposals. The project concludes that BLUETOURL is a useful and replicable tool for adaptive coastal tourism management.

Keywords: Coastal tourism, Climate change adaptation, Tourism resilience, Vulnerability assessment, Decision-support tool

Cite this abstract: Maestro, M., Chica Ruiz, J.A., Arcila Garrido, M., de Andrés García, M., Ramírez Guerrero, G., García Onetti, J., Gasalla López, B. (2026). Decision-support tool for sustainable tourism planning in at-risk coastal destinations. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P9.

P10. Spatio-temporal characterization of seagrass meadows using UAV multispectral data and machine learning models

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Seagrass meadows are among the world's most productive marine ecosystems, but they are also among the most vulnerable to human activities and climate change. In this study, state-of-the-art machine learning algorithms (i.e. XGBoost, Support Vector Machine, Random Forest, and Neural Networks) applied to multispectral data captured using Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) technology are explored to determine the spatial coverage of marine macrophyte species in the Bay of Cádiz Natural Park (Spain), specifically in the Santibáñez study area, as well as their spatio-temporal evolution between 2021 and 2025. These results provide a useful tool for the active management and conservation of these valuable coastal habitats, as well as enable monitoring, at centimetre-level resolution, of their evolution and trends in recent years.

Keywords: Seagrass meadows, marine macrophytes, drones, artificial intelligence, machine learning.

Cite this abstract: Obrador, S., Xanxo, R., Navarro, G., Román, A. (2026). Spatio-temporal characterization of seagrass meadows using UAV multispectral data and machine learning models. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P10.

P11. Use of machine learning models and unmanned aerial vehicle data for the spatio-temporal analysis of chinstrap penguin colonies on Deception Island (Antarctica).

Lucía Navarro-Miragaya, Alejandro Román, Antonio Tovar-Sánchez, Gabriel Navarro

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Antarctica is being affected by climate change, such that some of its coastal ecosystems – like chinstrap penguin colonies – are experiencing changes in many different ways. Therefore, it is essential to develop accurate methodologies to monitor the evolution of their habitats, and to assess their spatio-temporal variability in recent years. Here, we propose a machine learning approach trained using unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) multispectral imagery to improve the accuracy of characterizing different penguin colonies on Deception Island (Antarctica) through upscaling to satellite data. This characterization is complemented by an estimation of penguin population trends over the past five years. Our results demonstrate how drones can complement the limitations of satellite imagery, as, with the support of emerging artificial intelligence algorithms, the assessment of the evolution and changes of these colonies under climate change scenarios – as well as the adoption of measures for their conservation and protection – has become a reality.

Keywords: Drones, Artificial Intelligence, Upscaling, Penguin Colony, Sentinel-2

Cite this abstract: Navarro-Miragaya, L., Román, A., Tovar-Sánchez, A., Navarro, G. (2026). Use of machine learning models and unmanned aerial vehicle data for the spatio-temporal analysis of chinstrap penguin colonies on Deception Island (Antarctica). In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P11.

P12. Remote-sensing tools for mapping invasive *Rugulopteryx okamurae* seaweed strandings on a Strait of Gibraltar beach

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Massive beach strandings of the invasive seaweed *Rugulopteryx okamurae* are severely affecting coastlines across southern Europe, generating significant environmental and socio-economic challenges. When accumulated on beaches, the decomposition of this algal biomass produces foul odours, degrades coastal landscapes, contributes to greenhouse gas emissions, and negatively impacts tourism, often requiring costly removal operations. This highlights the need for systematic and timely monitoring to support effective strandings management. We present a twofold satellite-based monitoring approach applied to Los Lances Beach (Tarifa, Cadiz), located in the Strait of Gibraltar. The Bointertidal Mapper processes Sentinel-2 imagery to map *R. okamurae* accumulations along the beach, while a web-based visualization platform provides near-real-time access to processed satellite data. Both tools are published in open access and are intuitive to use, requiring no prior expertise in remote sensing. The approach supports near-real-time decision-making, is easily transferable to other affected areas, and enables more efficient and proactive coastal management.

Keywords: *User-friendly toolbox, invasive seaweed, beach strandings, low tide, Normalized Difference Vegetation Index*

Cite this abstract: Haro, S., Navarro, G., Caballero, I. (2026). Remote-sensing tools for mapping invasive *Rugulopteryx okamurae* seaweed strandings on a Strait of Gibraltar beach. In: *EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P12.*

P13. Need for standardized indices assessing climate vulnerability in coastal tourist destinations.

Beatriz Gasalla López, Juan Adolfo Chica Ruiz, Manuel Arcila Garrido

Departamento de Historia, Geografía y Filosofía, Universidad de Cádiz

Spanish coasts, the engine of sun and beach tourism, face high degradation due to human pressure and climate change. The use of indices is essential to assess coastal vulnerability and support decision-making. This study analyzes 43 works on climate vulnerability indices in coastal areas. Results show a lack of conceptual consensus (necessity to align with IPCC definitions) and high methodological variability. Effects like erosion and flooding are prioritized; however, factors critical to the tourism sector like rising temperature are often ignored. Critically, only 11.6% of the analyzed works consider the tourism sector. This inconsistency and lack of standardization limit practical applicability. We emphasize the urgent need to standardize evaluations and propose the development of a municipal-scale index that integrates the tourism sector to guide effective management and planning in coastal destinations.

Keywords: *climate change, vulnerability index, coastal tourist destinations*

Cite this abstract: Gasalla López, B., Chica Ruiz, J.A., Arcila Garrido, M. (2026). Need for standardized indices assessing climate vulnerability in coastal tourist destinations. In: *EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P13.*

P14. Macroalgal canopies as thermal refuges against coastal warming

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³ *Instituto de investigación y formación Agraria y Pesquera*

⁴ *Centro Oceanográfico de Vigo, Instituto Español de Oceanografía (IEO), CSIC*

⁵ *Centro de Investigación Marina, Universidade de Vigo, EcoCost, Facultade de Ciencias do Mar*

⁶ *Smithsonian Environmental Research Center*

In recent decades, seawater temperatures in the NE Atlantic have increased, and more intense and frequent marine heatwaves (MHWs) have emerged as significant threats to coastal ecosystems. The resilience of natural communities is a key factor modulating ecosystem vulnerability, yet the role of biogenic habitats, such as canopy-forming macroalgal forests, in buffering against heat stress remains poorly understood. Here, we assessed the thermal mitigation capacity of macroalgal forests, focusing on the genus *Cystoseira* sensu lato, and its effect on associated macroinvertebrates. Using a mesocosm experiment, we exposed synthetic macroalgal forests with different densities and associated gastropods to a simulated MHW during low tide. Our results confirmed the heat-stress buffering capacity of macroalgal forests on macrofauna, though this effect was highly dependent on forest integrity, i.e. patchiness. Overall, these findings highlight the potential of macroalgal forests as ecological refuges under future ocean warming conditions.

Keywords: *Coastal warming; canopy-forming algae; microclimate regulation; benthic system; manipulative experiment.*

Cite this abstract: Soler-Fajardo, A., Bernal-Ibañez, A., Cacabelos, E., Olabarria, C., Gestoso, I. (2026). Macroalgal canopies as thermal refuges against coastal warming. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P14.

P15. Oceanographic and trophic forcing of zooplankton dynamics on the northeastern shelf of the Gulf of Cádiz

Susana Rodríguez-Gálvez¹, Pablo Almaraz¹, Diego Macías², Manuel Fernández-Barba¹ and Javier Ruiz¹

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² *European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC)*

The aim of this study is to determine how environmental and trophic forcing defines mesozooplankton dynamics and the degree of coupling with phytoplankton across the northeastern shelf of the Gulf of Cádiz. Monthly mesozooplankton time series were analysed using Dynamic Factor Analysis to identify dominant temporal modes of variability and their spatial structure, and were related to time series of environmental variables and chlorophyll. A strong and coherent seasonal signal is identified as the main mode of mesozooplankton variability, modulated by regional environmental forcing, whose spatial expression defines domains with differentiated temporal responses. When considered together with phytoplankton dynamics, these domains exhibit contrasting degrees of trophic coupling, modulated by environmental forcing across the shelf. This work reveals that the pelagic ecosystem of the northeastern shelf of the Gulf of Cádiz is structured into domains with distinct trophic responses, where mesozooplankton integrates environmental forcing, conditioning its coupling with phytoplankton and energy transfer efficiency.

Keywords: *Mesozooplankton, Dynamic Factor Analysis, Gulf of Cádiz*

Cite this abstract: Rodríguez-Gálvez, S., Almaraz, P., Macías, D., Fernández-Barba, M., Ruiz, J. (2026). Oceanographic and trophic forcing of zooplankton dynamics on the northeastern shelf of the Gulf of Cádiz. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P15.

P16. Biogeochemistry and dynamics in metal-contaminated estuarine sediments

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The Huelva Estuary, formed by the confluence of the Tinto and Odiel rivers, is affected by metal contamination linked to mining activities in the Iberian Pyrite Belt (SW Iberian Peninsula) since pre-Roman times. The pH gradient generated by the mixing of acidic river waters (pH ~3.0) with alkaline seawater (pH ~8.0) plays a major role in contaminant attenuation through precipitation and dilution processes. Consequently, estuarine sediments show high concentrations of metals (e.g., up to 140 g kg⁻¹ Fe, 36 g kg⁻¹ S, 3 g kg⁻¹ As, and 2 g kg⁻¹ Cu). To assess the biogeochemical interactions controlling contaminant mobility, DNA metabarcoding was applied to surface sediments (0–15 cm) with different contamination levels. The sediments, mainly silty loams, exhibited pH values between 4.0 and 8.0 under predominantly oxidizing conditions and were mineralogically dominated by quartz and phyllosilicates with Fe and Cu sulfides and oxides. Lower microbial diversity was observed in highly contaminated sediments, which were enriched in Fe- and S-oxidizing and sulfate-reducing microorganisms. These results highlight the key role of microbial processes in regulating metal mobility in contaminated estuarine sediments under changing environmental conditions.

Keywords: *Ría de Huelva, pH, microbial diversity, metabarcoding, REDOX*

Cite this abstract: Basallote, M.D., Montero-Beltran, J., Neculita, C., Pakostova, E. (2026). Biogeochemistry and dynamics in metal-contaminated estuarine sediments. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P16.

P17. Eco-sustainable alternative extraction protocols for the extraction of *P.glauca* collagen.

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Increasingly restrictive ocean environmental policies have intensified the need for more sustainable biomolecule production. In this context, green extraction methodologies with reduced environmental impact represent a promising alternative. Conventional collagen extraction protocols rely on chemically harmful, resource-intensive, and time-consuming processes, which have largely limited their application to laboratory-scale production. This study explores eco-sustainable collagen extraction from *Prionace glauca* skin by-products by reducing the concentrations of key chemicals (NaOH and acetic acid), achieving yields and characteristics comparable to those reported in the literature using higher concentrations. Additionally, the integration of physical techniques, including ultrasound and high-shear homogenization, was evaluated as a strategy to shorten extraction time. These results highlight the potential of environmentally friendly extraction approaches to support the industrial-scale production of marine collagen.

Keywords: *collagen, Prionace glauca, green extraction methodologies, sustainable production*

Cite this abstract: Pérez-Martín, R.I., Blanco, M., Ramos, P., Sanz, N., Sotelo, C.G. (2026). Eco-sustainable alternative extraction protocols for the extraction of *P.glauca* collagen. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P17.

P18. ALIMAR Project: valorization of mediterranean marine biomass

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The objective of the ALIMAR project was to analyse the possibilities of management and valorisation of several marine species present in the Mediterranean Sea, jellyfish (*Rhizostoma pulmo*, *Cotylorhiza tuberculata*) and blue crab (*Callinectes sapidus*). The isolation of collagen from jellyfish was studied using conventional methods and by supercritical extraction as a more sustainable alternative and even higher yield. Likewise, the collagen obtained was characterized by SDS-PAGE electrophoresis and the amino acid profile. Collagen yields ranged from 2.5–18% dry basis with conventional methods and up to 32% using supercritical fluid extraction. Chitin was obtained from blue crab shells by enzymatic and chemical treatment, characterized by determination of its proximal composition,

the C/N ratio and FTIR spectroscopy. Chitin showed an 8.66% yield dry basis with high purity (Degree of Acetylation \approx 90%). In conclusion, Jellyfish represent promising sources of collagen, though process optimization and deeper characterization are required to ensure industrial viability and sustainability.

Keywords: *jellyfish collagen , blue crab chitin , supercritical fluid extraction , sustainable biomaterials, Mediterranean species*

Cite this abstract: Ramos, P., Blanco, M., Sotelo, C.G., Muñoz, A., Taboada, L., Bellido, J.M., Pérez-Martín, R.I. (2026). ALIMAR Project: valorization of mediterranean marine biomass. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P18.

P19. Environmental drivers of blue whiting recruitment: Insights from 20 years of observations

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The recruitment of marine fish is a complex process influenced by multiple ecological factors that often interact unpredictably, which makes accurate forecasting difficult. However, exceptional recruitment events offer valuable insights into the conditions that favor early survival. In 2020, the Spanish Bottom Trawl Survey on Porcupine Bank recorded the highest abundance of blue whiting recruits in a 20-year time series. To understand this anomaly, we analyzed historical recruitment patterns in relation to environmental variables, such as chlorophyll-a concentration, salinity, temperature, wind mixing, and ocean currents, derived from satellite observations and numerical models. Our findings suggest that the unusually weak winds during the spawning season promoted the formation of a stable Taylor column, which enhanced nutrient retention and primary productivity, as evidenced by the elevated levels of chlorophyll-a. Lagrangian transport models also revealed distinct larval dispersal patterns in 2020 compared to other years. These results underscore the impact of rare combinations of favorable conditions on recruitment success and inform adaptive fisheries management under climate change scenarios.

Keywords: *recruitment, environmental drivers, fisheries management*

Cite this abstract: Baldó, F., Chowdhury, M., González-Nuevo, G., Velasco, F., Laiz, I. (2026). Environmental drivers of blue whiting recruitment: Insights from 20 years of observations. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P19.

P20. Developing a tool to predict jellyfish arrivals to coastal areas in the Western Mediterranean Sea

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1. Objectives: The objective of this study is to develop a forecasting tool capable of predicting coastal arrivals of *Pelagia noctiluca*, the species responsible for most jellyfish incidents in the Western Mediterranean Sea. 2. Methodology: We trained a data-driven machine-learning model using a unique long-term dataset of jellyfish observations collected since 2014, combined with oceanographic and atmospheric environmental variables. The model produces spatially explicit forecasts of jellyfish arrival probability and relative abundance up to two days in advance along the Balearic coastline. 3. Results: On average, model predictions agree with historical observations in approximately 80% of cases. 4. Implications: Current efforts focus on operationalizing the

model for near-real-time forecasting and integrating the outputs into a user-friendly mobile application. This approach demonstrates the potential of combining long-term ecological monitoring and machine learning to support marine hazard mitigation and coastal management in the Mediterranean Sea.

Keywords: *Pelagia noctiluca; Mediterranean Sea; Forecasting*

Cite this abstract: Ottmann, D., León-Cobo, M.J., Tintoré, J., Ruiz, J., Moragues, E., Grau, A.M., Prieto, L. (2026). Developing a tool to predict jellyfish arrivals to coastal areas in the Western Mediterranean Sea. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P20.

P21. Model-based assessment of physical forcings influencing the presence of the jellyfish *Pelagia noctiluca* in the Balearic Archipelago

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In recent years, massive jellyfish blooms have gained relevance due to their ecological and socio-economic impacts, particularly on health, fisheries and tourism. This study aims to evaluate how physical forcings influence the coastal presence of the jellyfish *Pelagia noctiluca* in the Balearic Islands. A comprehensive database of daily jellyfish sightings from 2014 to the present was compiled in collaboration with the Government of the Balearic Islands and the Balearic Islands Coastal Observation and Forecasting System (SOCIB). These data were combined with oceanographic and biogeochemical model outputs to apply modeling techniques identifying environmental drivers of jellyfish occurrence. Results show that coastal bathymetry, current intensity, temperature, chlorophyll concentration and seasonality are correlated with the presence of *P. noctiluca*. These findings highlight the potential for developing predictive tools to anticipate jellyfish arrivals, supporting preventive management measures and mitigating impacts on human health and coastal economic activities.

Keywords: *Scyphozoa, stochastic modeling, oceanography, marine currents, Balearic Islands.*

Cite this abstract: León-Cobo, M.J., Ottmann, D., Ruiz, J., Moragues, E., Grau, A.M., Tintoré, J., Prieto, L. (2026). Model-based assessment of physical forcings influencing the presence of the jellyfish *Pelagia noctiluca* in the Balearic Archipelago. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P21.

P22. Combined effects of sunscreens and warming on mussel larval behaviour

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The growing input of sunscreens into coastal waters poses a potential risk to marine ecosystems, where they can exert sublethal effects on marine invertebrates, especially during sensitive early life stages. Simultaneously, ocean warming may alter organismal vulnerability to chemical stressors. This work aims to evaluate the combined effects of temperature and sunscreen exposure on larval swimming behaviour of the mussel *Mytilus galloprovincialis*. Larvae were exposed for 48 hours to four concentrations (0, 0.05, 5 and 100 mg/L) of four commercial sunscreens, including two labeled as eco friendly and two conventional formulations, under two temperature scenarios (18 °C and 20 °C). Larval swimming speed was quantified from video recordings using AnimalTA software. Swimming speed decreased consistently with increasing sunscreen concentration, with significant reductions at 100 mg/L relative to controls at both temperatures ($p < 0.05$). These findings highlight behavioural impairment as a sensitive endpoint and underscore the need to consider climate related warming when assessing sunscreen ecotoxicity.

Keywords: *sunscreens, climate change, larval behaviour, Mytilus galloprovincialis*

Cite this abstract: Castillo, G., Aranda-Quirós, V., Úbeda, M., Rodríguez-Romero, A. (2026). Combined effects of sunscreens and warming on mussel larval behaviour. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P22.

P23. AI Drone-Satellite upscaling of ecological communities: Bay of Cádiz

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The so-called Blue Carbon ecosystems (BCE) are widely distributed along coastlines around the world and are highly vulnerable to global changes. The development of methods enabling synoptic and multi-temporal monitoring of their spatial extent is thus essential. Here, we developed a new machine learning-based approach for the upscaling from high-resolution drone data to satellite remote sensing for an accurate mapping of the distribution and evolution of BCE (i.e. seagrass meadows, saltmarshes, and MPB) in the tidal flats of the Cádiz Bay (Spain) during the last 5 years. This approach will explore the possibility of improving previous Sentinel-2 imagery derived estimations, bridging the existing knowledge gap in estimating the coverage of these ecosystems, in the context of refining current carbon budgets at local and regional scales.

Keywords: Blue carbon; Machine Learning; Unmanned Aerial Vehicle; Remote Sensing; coastal

Cite this abstract: Alonso, I., Haro, S., Navarro, G., Xanxo, R., Román, A. (2026). AI Drone-Satellite upscaling of ecological communities: Bay of Cádiz. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P23.

P24. Bed-level tools for monitoring sediment dynamics: flume validation and field testing

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Monitoring short-term changes in surface sediment elevation is fundamental to understanding sediment dynamics in coastal environments, yet commonly used bed-level monitoring methods have not been cross-validated under both controlled and field conditions. This study experimentally evaluates the potential biases to reduce the uncertainty of two widely used and accessible bed level monitoring tools: sedimentation plates (without string, with string, and with string and buoy) and rebars. The two methods were tested under controlled conditions in a hydraulic flume with sandy substrates under unidirectional and oscillatory flow regimes (11 and 23 cm s⁻¹) and validated in the field within a *Zostera marina* meadow in the Bay of Santander (Spain) over one year. Hydrodynamic interference of the structural components was assessed using Reynolds numbers. Across all flow regimes and field habitats, erosion rates did not differ significantly among methods. Although the buoy produced localized turbulence, the resulting shear stress was well below critical erosion thresholds. These results demonstrate that sedimentation plates and rebars can be used interchangeably to obtain reliable bed-level measurements, providing a validated and cost-effective framework for sediment monitoring in coastal and (vegetated) aquatic ecosystems.

Keywords: sediment transport, field methods, seagrasses, hydraulic flume, Reynolds number

Cite this abstract: Rodríguez-Arias, L., Mazarrasa, I., Marin-Diaz, B., Alcoverro, T., Ondiviela, B., Pagès, J.F., Infantes, E. (2026). Bed-level tools for monitoring sediment dynamics: flume validation and field testing. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P24.

P25. *Scrobicularia plana*, a Biomonitor for Heavy Metals in the Guadalquivir River Estuary

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Estuaries are transitional systems between the sea and rivers and are subject to strong anthropogenic pressure. The Guadalquivir River estuary is the main estuary in the south of the Iberian Peninsula, where mining activity has been carried out for centuries. The presence in the estuary of the species *Scrobicularia plana* (bivalve mollusk), which inhabits the sediments, is of particular interest due to its potential use for biomonitoring pollution. The objective of this study was to compile and analyze the information generated by our group in the context of different projects in order to establish baseline levels and identify pollution events. To this end, samples of this species were collected at various stations in the Guadalquivir estuary and the organisms were freeze-dried and digested, and the concentration was subsequently quantified by ICP-OES or ICP-MS. Results covering a period of 25 years are presented. These results are of great interest for the identification of pollution events and for ecosystem management.

Keywords: *Scrobicularia plana*, metal pollution, Guadalquivir estuary, biomonitor

Cite this abstract: Trombini, C., Michán, C., de Alda, M.L., Alhama-Carmona, J., Blasco, J. (2026). *Scrobicularia plana* a Biomonitor for Heavy Metals in the Guadalquivir River Estuary. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P25.

P26. Environmental compatibility of DHHB demonstrated by marine biodegradation behavior

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This work investigated the biodegradation behaviour of the UV filter Diethylamino Hydroxybenzoyl Hexyl Benzoate(DHHB), an organic UV filter widely used in cosmetic formulations as a new-generation UVA filter. Biodegradation was assessed according to the OECD 306 guideline by incubating DHHB at a concentration of 50 ug/L in natural seawater supplemented with mineral medium. Samples were collected over a 35-day experimental period and analysed by UHPLC-QTOF, monitoring changes in normalized signal intensity over time. An abiotic control was included to exclude non-biological processes such as hydrolysis or adsorption. The results showed clear evidence of biodegradation during the experiment time. Nearly complete degradation was observed after 20 days, and the substance shows a phenomena of adsorption in the glass wall of reactor. Overall, these findings indicate that DHHB exhibits rapid biodegradation in marine environments, supporting its use as a sustainable UVA filter with a low potential for environmental persistence and bioaccumulation.

Keywords: *biodegradation*, *eco-friendly UV filter*, *environmental impact*

Cite this abstract: Cerone, V., Perugini, P., Pintado-Herrera, M.G. (2026). *Environmental compatibility of DHHB demonstrated by marine biodegradation behavior*. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P26.

P27. MARVIVA: Designing biodegradable structures for seagrass restoration

Alba Yamuza Magdaleno, Isabel Casal Porras, Fernando G. Brun Murillo

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The objective of the MARVIVA project is to develop biodegradable biopolymer meshes adapted to the specific characteristics of different species of seagrasses for effective ecological restoration. MARVIVA will be carried out by researchers from the Blue Carbon Laboratory at the University of Cádiz and the Plastics Technology Institute, which will contribute its extensive knowledge of biodegradable materials. These structures will be manufactured

from a biopolymer that guarantees their biodegradation in the aquatic environment, maintaining their functionality for the time required to ensure the repopulation of seagrass and complete degradation after use, thus avoiding the generation of waste that could have a negative impact on biodiversity. The structures will then be validated under controlled conditions in flow tanks and reclaimed saltmarshes. The restoration of seagrass meadows will maintain and improve the functions and services they provide, highlighting their capacity to store carbon in the sediment, contributing to climate change mitigation.

Keywords: *seagrass, restoration, biodegradable structures, biopolymer, blue carbon*

Cite this abstract: Yamuza Magdaleno, A., Casal Porras, I., Brun Murillo, F.G. (2026). MARVIVA: Designing biodegradable structures for seagrass restoration. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P27.

P28. Optimisation of seagrass restoration techniques in the Bay of Cádiz

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University of Cádiz

The main objective of this pilot study, conducted within the framework of the FINOCAME project, was to determine the best replanting and growth method for seagrass in the Bay of Cádiz. To this end, *Cymodocea nodosa* and *Zostera noltei* species were planted in three biodegradable coconut meshes (BCM) of different thicknesses, and two sediment types (muddy and sandy) with different organic matter content, including a control without BCM. Plantings were carried out in a flow-through tank for 6 months, under natural light and temperature conditions. Every 15 days, the shoots planted in each treatment were counted, and their growth and survival were analysed. Preliminary results indicate that the thinnest BCM promoted the highest shoot growth in both species, compared to treatments without BCM. *Zostera noltei* showed greater growth in muddy sediment, whereas *Cymodocea nodosa* showed no significant differences between sediment types. These preliminary results provide valuable insights for optimizing seagrass restoration methodologies.

Keywords: *Seagrass, restoration, coconut meshes, blue carbon*

Cite this abstract: Casal-Porras, I., Yamuza-Magdaleno, A., Calafat, C., Brun, F.G. (2026). Optimisation of seagrass restoration techniques in the Bay of Cádiz. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P28.

P29. Carbon restoration in abandoned bivalve farms via seagrass recolonisation

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This study aimed to assess whether abandoned bivalve farms in the Ria Formosa lagoon (southern Portugal) can recover organic carbon (OC) storage through natural recolonisation by the seagrass *Zostera noltii*, compared with original undisturbed seagrass meadows lost during farm construction. Sediment properties and OC stocks were analysed in three intertidal settings: active oyster farms, active clam farms, and abandoned farms naturally recolonised by seagrass. Recolonised areas showed higher organic matter content, lower bulk density, and OC stocks in the upper 25 cm of sediment up to four times higher than those in clam farms and approximately 1.6 times higher than in oyster farms, reaching values comparable to nearby undisturbed meadows. Intermediate OC stocks in oyster farms likely reflect legacy carbon from former seagrass or organic inputs associated with oyster cultivation. These findings demonstrate that abandoned bivalve farms can naturally regain their blue carbon function without active restoration, highlighting their potential role in cost-effective coastal carbon management and climate mitigation strategies.

Keywords: *bivalve farming, seagrass, blue carbon, legacy carbon deposits, passive restoration*

Cite this abstract: de los Santos, C.B., Román, M., Paone, C., Olabarria, C., Santos, R. (2026). Carbon restoration in abandoned bivalve farms via seagrass recolonisation. In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P29.

P30. Identificación y cuantificación de microplásticos en bivalvos costeros (*Scrobicularia plana*)

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El estudio realizado tuvo como objetivo la identificación y cuantificación de microplásticos (MPs) en la especie bivalva *Scrobicularia plana* además de evaluar su papel como bioindicador en zonas costeras del litoral andaluz occidental. Se muestrearon tres áreas con alta influencia antrópica: Bahía de Cádiz, Estuario del Guadalquivir y Costa de Huelva. Las muestras se trataron mediante digestión química posterior separación por tamaños y caracterización mediante micro-FTIR para la determinación de tipos y concentraciones de polímeros. Los resultados obtenidos mostraron la presencia generalizada de MPs en todas las zonas, con una predominancia de fragmentos frente a fibras, especialmente en las fracciones mayores. Se identificaron ocho polímeros diferentes, siendo el politetrafluoroetileno y copolímeros los más frecuentes, evidenciando una contaminación heterogénea vinculada a la presión antrópica. El estudio resalta la necesidad de monitoreo en las zonas costeras para evaluar el riesgo de los MPs sobre el medio ambiente y la salud humana.

Keywords: Microplásticos, *Scrobicularia plana*, Bioindicador, micro-FTIR, contaminación costera

Cite this abstract: Sánchez Vélez, M., Trombini, C., Coello Oviedo, D., Rodríguez Barroso, R., Egea-Corbacho, Á. (2026). Identificación y cuantificación de microplásticos en bivalvos costeros (*Scrobicularia plana*). In: EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026. EuroMarine Network. P30.

P31. Tetrodotoxins in the Algarve: Current evidence

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Introduction Tetrodotoxin (TTX) is a potent neurotoxin, first identified in fish from the Tetraodontidae family, but also detected in marine invertebrates. A Human poisoning episode after consumption of trumpet shell *Charonia lampas*, likely caught off the Portuguese mainland southern coast – Algarve, together with the increasing reports of TTX in European waters, led the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) to recommend maximum safe limits for Human consumption of shellfish meat. However, data on temporal and species incidence of TTX are lacking. Objectives and methods. This presentation will summarize recent studies conducted at CCMAR aimed at evaluating potential vectors, tissue distribution, and seasonal variability of TTX and its analogues in marine organisms from Algarve. TTXs were analyzed using liquid chromatography–high resolution mass spectrometry (LC-HRMS) in trumpet shells, sea stars (*Astropecten aranciatus*), and intertidal crabs (*Afruca tangeri* and *Carcinus maenas*). Discussion and conclusions. Trumpet shell represents a potential public health risk due to its capacity to accumulate TTX and analogues while being consumed as a gourmet food. Although these toxins are mainly concentrated in non-edible tissues, unsafe levels may be transferred to edible parts, emphasizing the need for European regulations to monitor TTX in seafood and to inform consumers about safe preparation practices. The origin of TTX in trumpet shells remains uncertain, but the detection of TTX and its analogues in their prey, the sea star, supports an exogenous acquisition pathway through the food web. Additionally, the occurrence of TTX analogues in crab species suggests the presence of multiple potential vectors along the Algarve coast, raising further questions about the risk of contamination in other commercially relevant marine species and the ecological dynamics of TTX transfer.

Keywords: *Emerging Biotoxins, Public Health, Seafood Safety, Fisheries, Aquaculture*

Cite this abstract: Lage, S. (2026). *Tetrodotoxins in the Algarve: Current evidence*. In: *EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026*. EuroMarine Network. P31.

P32. What happens when sperm meets egg? New Insight

Luigia Santella, Nunzia Limatola, Jong Tai Chun

Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn

Since Oskar Hertwig's seminal observation in 1876 of the fusion between the sperm pronucleus and that of a sea urchin egg, many fundamental questions about the mechanism of fertilization have arisen. Sea urchins have become ideal models for studying fertilization due to their readily available, abundant, and transparent gametes. These features have facilitated detailed investigations into the essential role of the protein bindin, which is exposed on the sperm acrosomal filament and mediates species-specific interactions with egg surface receptors in response to egg jelly. Gamete fusion triggers a rapid change in the egg's membrane potential—known as the fast block to polyspermy—which prevents additional sperm from fusing. Subsequently, calcium-induced cortical granule exocytosis modifies the egg's outer layer to form a fertilization envelope, providing a slower, more permanent block to polyspermy. The fertilization process of starfish and sea urchin eggs will be discussed in light of live-cell imaging and electron microscopy results, leading to the formulation of new alternative hypotheses. Time-lapse videos will also be presented.

Keywords: *Starfish and sea urchin eggs, fertilization, acrosome reaction, calcium, actin*

Cite this abstract: Santella, L., Limatola, N., Chun, J.T. (2026). *What happens when sperm meets egg? New Insight*. In: *EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026*. EuroMarine Network. P32.

P33. Assessing beach safety within the big five framework

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The “Big Five” model classifies beaches according to user preferences, highlighting safety, facilities, water quality, absence of solid waste, and scenery. Among these, safety is the attribute most directly linked to user health, well-being, and coastal management effectiveness. In this study, safety is defined as the absence of hazardous currents or other natural risks that may cause accidents, with drowning—primarily due to rip currents—being the most severe and frequent incident. The objective is to develop a methodology for analyzing beach safety within the Big Five framework. An exhaustive bibliographic review was conducted to identify the most suitable indicators, and a methodological matrix was created for its evaluation. The study develops a semiquantitative management tool to improve the assessment of coastal bathing areas. This approach provides local administrations with a structured tool to assess and enhance safety management, while integrating user-centered criteria into coastal tourism quality evaluation.

Keywords: *Coastal assessment; Beach management; Semiquantitative tool; coastal risks*

Cite this abstract: Molina, R., Anfuso, G., Antelo, B.J., Pérez, J.J.M. (2026). *Assessing beach safety within the big five framework*. In: *EuroMarine Open Science Days 2026 – Book of Abstracts, Cádiz, Spain, 10–11 March 2026*. EuroMarine Network. P33.

P34. PLOATECH: Engineering Marine Science

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PLOATECH advances marine technology by designing innovative autonomous systems to collect data in places and conditions where traditional monitoring is difficult, effectively addressing critical gaps in our understanding of the ocean. With more than 25 years of experience, PLOATECH translates marine science requirements into robust, operational technologies that support long-term, high-resolution, and cost-effective ocean observation. Within the RAMONES project, PLOATECH developed low-power, pressure-tolerant instrumentation for in situ radioactivity monitoring, integrating these sensors into autonomous gliders and benthic observatories to support continuous and reliable environmental measurements. In the NEXTMARINE project, PLOATECH is advancing non-invasive observation of fragile marine ecosystems through high-resolution 3D/4D seabed mapping and hyperspectral imaging, contributing to improved ecosystem assessment and impact monitoring. Complementary initiatives such as SANTORY focus on the deployment of advanced seafloor observatories that enable sustained monitoring of key ocean variables. By combining autonomous robotics, custom sensing technologies, and AI-enabled data processing, PLOATECH supports scientific research, environmental protection, and evidence-based decision making for sustainable ocean management.

Keywords: Autonomous Ocean Observation, Marine Robotics, In Situ Sensing Technologies, Long-Term Marine Monitoring, Environmental Intelligence

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